

SOME VARIATIONS OF q -ANALOGUES OF SUN AND TAURASO'S CONGRUENCE

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Received: 7/12/23, Revised: 10/9/23, Accepted: 11/27/23, Published: 12/8/23

Abstract

We establish some q -congruences related to Sun and Tauraso's congruence:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p^r-1} \frac{1}{2^k} \binom{2k}{k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p^r-1}{2}} \pmod{p},$$

where p is an odd prime and r is a positive integer.

1. Introduction

Congruences involving central binomial coefficients $\binom{2n}{n}$ have attracted many experts' attention in recent years. In 2010, Sun and Tauraso [6] proved that for any odd prime p and positive integer r ,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p^r-1} \frac{1}{2^k} \binom{2k}{k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p^r-1}{2}} \pmod{p}. \quad (1)$$

Sun [5] showed that (1) also holds modulo p^2 in the same year.

Subsequently, Guo and Zeng [4, Corollary 4.2] first established a q -analogue of (1) as follows:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k}{(q; q)_k} q^k \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} q^{\frac{n^2-1}{4}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \quad (2)$$

where n is an odd positive integer. We remark that Guo [2] further showed that (2) holds modulo $\Phi_n(q)^2$. Here and throughout the paper, the q -shifted factorials are given by $(a; q)_n = (1-a)(1-aq) \cdots (1-aq^{n-1})$ for $n \geq 1$ and $(a; q)_0 = 1$. The n th cyclotomic polynomial is given by

$$\Phi_n(q) = \prod_{\substack{1 \leq k \leq n \\ (n,k)=1}} (q - \zeta^k),$$

where ζ denotes a primitive n th root of unity.

For more q -congruences related to (1), we refer the interested reader to [1, 3, 7, 8]. It is worth mentioning that Guo [3, Theorem 1] recently established two new q -analogues of (1):

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k+1} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{3}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{4}$$

where n is an odd positive integer.

The first aim of the paper is to give two different q -analogues of (1) as follows.

Theorem 1. *For any positive odd integer n , we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4(k+1)} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} (1 - q + q^2) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{5}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k+1} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} (2 - q) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{6}$$

Letting $q \rightarrow 1$ and $n = p^r$ in the Theorem 1, (5) and (6) reduce to (1). So (5) and (6) are q -analogues of(1).

Gu and Guo [1, Theorem 1] established q -analogues of the following two congruences related to (1):

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p^r-1} \frac{1}{2^k(2k-1)} \binom{2k}{k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p^r-1}{2}} \pmod{p}, \tag{7}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p^r-1} \frac{2k+1}{2^k} \binom{2k}{k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p^r+1}{2}} \pmod{p}.$$

The second aim of the paper is to give two new q -analogues of (7) as follows.

Theorem 2. *For any positive odd integer $n \geq 3$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{-1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{8}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{-1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} (2q - 1) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{9}$$

Next, we shall extend Theorems 1 and 2 through Carlitz’s identity.

Theorem 3. *For any integer d and odd positive integer n with $n > 2 \mid d \mid -1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{10}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \frac{2 - q^{2d+1}}{q^{2d+1}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{11}$$

In fact, Theorem 2 is a special case of Theorem 3 for $d = -1$.

Theorem 4. *For any integer d and odd positive integer n with $n > 2 \mid d \mid -1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k+1} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} q^{-2d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{12}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4(k+1)} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \frac{q^2 + 1 - q^{2d+1}}{q^{4d}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{13}$$

Letting $q \rightarrow 1$ in Theorems 3 and 4 and using L’hospital rule, we are led to the following result.

Corollary 1. *For any integer d , positive integer r and odd prime p with $p > 2 \mid d \mid -1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p^r-1} \frac{2^k (d + \frac{1}{2})_k}{k!} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p^r-1}{2}+d} \pmod{p}, \tag{14}$$

where $(x)_k = x(x + 1) \cdots (x + k - 1)$.

We remark that letting $d = 0$ and $n = p^r$ in (14) reduces to (1).

2. Proof of Theorem 1

Let

$$A_1(k, q) = \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k}.$$

It is easy to check that

$$(1 - q^{2k}) A_1(k, q) = (1 - q^{2k-1}) (1 + q^{2k}) A_1(k - 1, q). \tag{15}$$

Summing both sides of (15) over k from 1 to $n - 1$ gives

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k}) A_1(k, q) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k-1}) (1 + q^{2k}) A_1(k - 1, q).$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k+1}) (1 + q^{2k+2}) A_1(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k}) A_1(k, q) \\ = (1 - q^{2n-1}) (1 + q^{2n}) A_1(n - 1, q). \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

We can rewrite (16) as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1 - q + q^2}{q} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{2k+1} A_1(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{4k+3} A_1(k, q) \\ = (1 - q^{2n-1} + q^{2n} - q^{4n-1}) \frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1} (-q^2; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q; q)_{n-1} (-q; q)_{n-1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Furthermore, note that (see [7, Lemma 2.2])

$$\frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q; q)_{n-1}} \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{18}$$

for any positive odd integer n .

Finally, combining (3), (17) and (18), we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4(k+1)} \equiv (-1)^{(n-1)/2} (1 - q + q^2) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

which completes the proof of (5).

We shall prove (6) similarly. Let

$$A_2(k, q) = \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k}.$$

It is easy to verify that

$$(1 - q^{2k}) A_2(k, q) = (1 - q^{2k-1}) (1 + q^{2k-2}) A_2(k - 1, q). \tag{19}$$

By using the same method as in the proof of (5), we can deduce from (19) that

$$\begin{aligned} (2 - q) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{2k} A_2(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{4k+1} A_2(k, q) \\ = (1 - q^{2n-1} + q^{2n-2} - q^{4n-3}) \frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1} (-1; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q; q)_{n-1} (-q; q)_{n-1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Combining (4), (18) and (20), we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k+1} \equiv (-1)^{(n-1)/2} (2 - q) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

as desired. □

3. Proof of Theorem 2

Let

$$B_1(k, q) = \frac{(q^{-1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k}.$$

It is easy to verify that

$$(1 - q^{2k}) B_1(k, q) = (1 - q^{2k-3}) (1 + q^{2k-2}) B_1(k - 1, q).$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k-1}) (1 + q^{2k}) B_1(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k}) B_1(k, q) \\ = (1 - q^{2n-3}) (1 + q^{2n-2}) B_1(n - 1, q). \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

By (18) and (21), we have

$$\begin{aligned} (2 - \frac{1}{q}) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{2k} B_1(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{4k-1} B_1(k, q) \\ = (1 + q^{2n-2}) (1 - q^{-1}) \frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1} (-1; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q; q)_{n-1} (-q; q)_{n-1}} \\ \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

On the other hand, we set

$$B_2(k, q) = \frac{(q^{-1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k}.$$

It is easy to check that

$$(1 - q^{2k}) B_2(k, q) = (1 - q^{2k-3}) (1 + q^{2k-2}) q^2 B_2(k - 1, q).$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k-1}) (1 + q^{2k}) q^2 B_2(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k}) B_2(k, q) \\ = (1 - q^{2n-3}) (1 + q^{2n-2}) q^2 B_2(n - 1, q). \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Note that

$$(1 - q^{2k-1}) B_2(k, q) = q^{2k} (1 - q^{-1}) A_2(k, q), \tag{24}$$

and

$$B_2(k, q) = q^{2k} B_1(k, q). \tag{25}$$

Substituting (24) and (25) into the left-hand side of (23) and using (18), we obtain

$$(q^2 - q) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (q^{4k} + q^{2k}) A_2(k, q) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (q^{2k} - q^{4k}) B_1(k, q) \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{26}$$

Furthermore, applying (4) and (6) to the left-hand side of (26) gives

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (q^{2k} - q^{4k}) B_1(k, q) \equiv 2(-1)^{(n-1)/2} (q - 1) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{27}$$

Finally, combining (22) and (27), we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{2k} B_1(k, q) \equiv (-1)^{(n+1)/2} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} q^{4k} B_1(k, q) \equiv (-1)^{(n+1)/2} (2q - 1) \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

which completes the proof of (8) and (9). □

4. Proof of Theorem 3

Firstly, letting $q \rightarrow q^{-1}$ in (10), we find that (10) is equivalent to

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-k^2-2dk} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}.$$

Recall the following Carlitz identity [9]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(a; q)_k (b; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} (-ab)^{n-k} q^{(n-k)(n+k-1)/2} = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(a; q)_{n+1} (-b)^k q^{\binom{k}{2}}}{(q; q)_k (q; q)_{n-k} (1 - aq^{n-k})}. \tag{28}$$

Letting $q \rightarrow q^2$, $n \rightarrow n - 1$, $a \rightarrow 2d + 1$ and $b \rightarrow -1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{(n-(1+k))(n+k+2d-1)} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n q^{k(k-1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_k (q^2; q^2)_{n-k-1} (1 - q^{2n+2d-2k-1})}. \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Note that $(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n$ has a factor $1 - q^n$ for $n > 2|d| - 1$. Thus, except for $k = \frac{n+2d-1}{2}$, the right-hand side of (29) is congruent to 0 modulo $\Phi_n(q)$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{(n-(1+k))(n+k+2d-1)} \\ & \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-k^2-2dk-2d+1} \\ & \equiv \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n q^{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}(\frac{n+2d-1}{2}-1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}} (q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n-2d-1}{2}} (1 - q^n)} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

For any integer s and n , we have

$$q^{sn} \equiv 1 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{31}$$

where the q -binomial coefficients are defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q = \begin{cases} \frac{(q; q)_n}{(q; q)_k (q; q)_{n-k}} & \text{if } 0 \leq k \leq n, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Simplifying the right-hand side of (30) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}}} \frac{q^{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}(\frac{n+2d-1}{2}-1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n-2d-1}{2}}(1-q^n)} \\ &= \frac{q^{(n+2d-1)(n+2d-3)/4}}{1-q^n} \frac{(q; q^2)_n(1-q^{2n+1})(1-q^{2n+3})\dots(1-q^{2n+2d-1})}{(1-q)(1-q^3)\dots(1-q^{2d-1})} \\ & \quad \times \frac{(1-q^{n-2d+1})(1-q^{n-2d+3})\dots(1-q^{n-1})}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n-1}{2}}(1-q^{n+1})(1-q^{n+3})\dots(1-q^{n+2d-1})} \\ & \equiv \left[\begin{matrix} n-1 \\ \frac{n-1}{2} \end{matrix} \right]_{q^2} \left[\begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ n-1 \end{matrix} \right] \frac{(-1)^d q^{(n+2d-1)(n+2d-3)/4-d^2}}{(-q; q)_{n-1}^2} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Note that (see [3, (2.5) and (2.6)])

$$\left[\begin{matrix} n-1 \\ \frac{n-1}{2} \end{matrix} \right]_{q^2} \equiv (-1)^{(n-1)/2} q^{(1-n^2)/4} (-q; q)^2 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)^2}, \tag{33}$$

and

$$\left[\begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ n-1 \end{matrix} \right] \equiv 1 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{34}$$

Substituting (33) and (34) into the right-hand side of (32), we get

$$\left[\begin{matrix} n-1 \\ \frac{n-1}{2} \end{matrix} \right]_{q^2} \left[\begin{matrix} 2n-1 \\ n-1 \end{matrix} \right] \frac{(-1)^d q^{(n+2d-1)(n+2d-3)/4-d^2}}{(-q; q)_{n-1}^2} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} q^{1-2d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{35}$$

Combining (30), (31), (32) and (35), we get

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-k^2-2dk-2d+1} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} q^{1-2d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

as desired.

Next we shall prove (11). Let

$$C_1(k, q, d) = \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k}.$$

It is easy to check that

$$(1 - q^{2k})C_1(k, q, d) = (1 - q^{2k+2d-1})(1 + q^{2k-2})C_1(k - 1, q, d). \tag{36}$$

Summing both side of (36) over k from 1 to $n - 1$, we get

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k})C_1(k, q, d) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 - q^{2k+2d-1})(1 + q^{2k-2})C_1(k - 1, q, d).$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (2 - q^{2d+1}) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k} - q^{2d+1} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k} \\ = (1 - q^{2n+2d-1} + q^{2n-2} - q^{4n+2d-3}) \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_{n-1} (-1; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}} &= \frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1} (1 - q^{2n+1})(1 - q^{2n+3}) \dots (1 - q^{2n+2d-3})}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1} (1 - q)(1 - q^3) \dots (1 - q^{2d-1})} \\ &\equiv \frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1} (1 - q^{2d-1})} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

By (18), we have

$$\frac{(q; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}} \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}, \tag{39}$$

for any integer $n \geq 3$.

Combining (31), (38) and (39), we find that the right-hand side of (37) is congruent to

$$(1 - q^{2n+2d-1} + q^{2n-2} - q^{4n+2d-3}) \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_{n-1} (-1; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}} \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{40}$$

Using (10), (37) and (40), we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-1; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4k} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \frac{2 - q^{2d+1}}{q^{2d+1}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}$$

as desired. □

5. Proof of Theorem 4

We first prove (12). Letting $q \rightarrow q^{-1}$ in (12), we find that (12) is equivalent to

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-(k+1)^2 - 2dk} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} q^{2d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}.$$

Letting $q \rightarrow q^2$, $n \rightarrow n - 1$, $a \rightarrow 2d + 1$ and $b \rightarrow -q^2$ in (28), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{(n-(1+k))(n+k+2d+1)} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n q^{k(k+1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_k (q^2; q^2)_{n-k-1} (1 - q^{2n+2d-2k-1})}. \end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

The right-hand side of (41) has a factor $1 - q^n$ for $n > 2|d| - 1$. Thus, for $k \neq \frac{n+2d-1}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{(n-(1+k))(n+k+2d+1)} \\ & \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-(k+1)^2 - 2dk - 2d} \\ & \equiv \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n q^{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}(\frac{n+2d-1}{2}+1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}} (q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n-2d-1}{2}} (1 - q^n)} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

Using the same method as in the proof of (32) and combining (31)–(34), we get

$$\frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_n q^{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}(\frac{n+2d+1}{2}+1)}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n+2d-1}{2}} (q^2; q^2)_{\frac{n-2d-1}{2}} (1 - q^n)} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{43}$$

Combining (42) and (43), we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{-(k+1)^2 - 2dk - 2d} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

which completes the proof of (12).

Next we shall prove (13). Let

$$D_1(k, q, d) = \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k}.$$

It is easy to check that

$$(1 - q^{2k})D_1(k, q, d) = (1 - q^{2k+2d-1})(1 + q^{2k})D_1(k - 1, q, d). \tag{44}$$

By using the same method as in the proof of (11), we can deduce from (44) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{q^2 + 1 - q^{2d+1}}{q} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{2k+1} \\ & - q^{2d-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4(k+1)} \\ & = (1 - q^{2n+2d-1} + q^{2n} - q^{4n+2d-1}) \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_{n-1} (-q^2; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Combining (31), (38) and (39), we find that the right-hand side of (45) is congruent to

$$(1 - q^{2n+2d-1} + q^{2n} - q^{4n+2d-1}) \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_{n-1} (-q^2; q^2)_{n-1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-1}} \equiv 0 \pmod{\Phi_n(q)}. \tag{46}$$

Finally, combining (12), (45) and (46), we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(q^{2d+1}; q^2)_k (-q^2; q^2)_k}{(q^2; q^2)_k} q^{4(k+1)} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}+d} \frac{q^2 + 1 - q^{2d+1}}{q^{4d}} \pmod{\Phi_n(q)},$$

as desired. □

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